

Tremonte-Freydefont, L., Fiori, M. & Wenger, M. (2023). Emotional intelligence and scholastic achievement in VET. A study among apprentices in healthcare and social care. In V. Tütlys, L. Vaitkutė & C. Nägele (Eds.), *Vocational Education and Training Transformations for Digital, Sustainable and Socially Fair Future. Proceedings of the 5th Crossing Boundaries Conference in Vocational Education and Training, Kaunas, 25. – 26. May* (pp. 443–449). European Research Network on Vocational Education and Training, VETNET, Vytautas Magnus University Education Academy, Institute of Educational Science. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7822707>

Emotional Intelligence and Scholastic Achievement in VET. A Study among Apprentices in Healthcare and Social Care

Tremonte-Freydefont, Laure

laure.tremonte@sfuvet.swiss, Swiss Federal university for Vocational Education and Training SFUVET

Fiori, Marina

marina.fiori@sfuvet.swiss, Swiss Federal university for Vocational Education and Training SFUVET

Wenger, Matilde

matilde.wenger@sfuvet.swiss, Swiss Federal university for Vocational Education and Training SFUVET

Abstract

Based on the literature showing the important role of emotional intelligence (EI) in well-being, academic achievement, but also in sustainability and employability, the present study addresses the question of the role of EI in training achievement in Vocational Education and Training (VET) context, and more especially in the health and social care sectors. Among the competences required to succeed in these VET programs, we posit that EI is an important component of the skills and abilities that apprentices need to be successful in their path to become professionals. 92 apprentices in health care and social care programs at the end of dual-track vocational training completed an online survey. Results confirm our hypothesis that EI as ability and as personality trait positively influence the final exam grades. These new findings reveal the importance of EI on training achievement in health and social care and open the path to new investigations exploring the role of EI in the VET context.

Keywords

emotional intelligence, Swiss VET system, healthcare sector, social care sector, apprenticeship's achievement

1 Introduction

1.1 Framework: emotional intelligence and achievement

Among the key competences of the 21st century, socio-emotional competences play a central role. In fact, they are linked to professional achievement and, more generally, to well-being and development in life (Bughin et al., 2018). These competences reflect the so-called emotional intelligence (EI), i.e., the individual's capacity to recognize his/her own and others' emotional reactions, but also to express, control, understand them and use this understanding for action. In this sense, EI and its associated competences play an important role in educational and training pathways, particularly to adapt optimally to these contexts. However, a recent literature review reports scarcity of European educational programs oriented to socio-emotional competences in Vocational Education and Training (VET) (Sauli et al., 2022). Moreover, EI as a competence necessary for sustainable development is emerging as a new research topic. Recent studies showed the positive influence of EI on management and sustainable development (Di Fabio & Saklofske, 2019). These new findings have a direct impact on how VET should consider EI and its role in the VET context. For example, when teachers responsible for apprentices do not possess the necessary competencies to engage in sustainability education, the potential of VET to become a viable tool in the society will decrease (Chinedu et al., 2023). In fact, by developing socio-emotional competences, individuals are more likely to become considerate not only for other people, but also for their environment.

The literature on EI has put forward two approaches to consider this concept: either as an ability (ability EI) or as a personality trait (trait EI). The ability approach considers EI as an ability or a form of objective intelligence, strongly associated with two components of the classic intelligence: the fluid and crystallized intelligences, involved in reasoning and solving new problems (Olderbak et al., 2018). The second approach conceives EI as a dispositional tendency, like a personality trait, and is then measured with self-reports (Petrides & Furnham, 2020). Trait EI or trait emotional self-efficacy is described as a constellation of emotional self-perceptions. Although these two approaches differ in their conceptualization and their measurement methods, they both consider intelligence as a distinct construct from the classic IQ. Moreover, both ability and trait EI are well-known predictors of academic achievement (MacCann et al., 2020). Results of interventions on emotional competences indicate that students with a higher EI level show more advantages than student with a lower EI level. For instance, they have a better management of conflicts and related emotions, a lower dropout rate, and show a better effectiveness at school, linked to social adaptation (Dowling et al., 2019; Nathanson et al., 2016). EI is also positively associated with general resilience and is correlated to employability, self-efficacy, and decision making in young adults (Di Fabio & Kenny, 2015).

In addition to the predictive function of EI with regard to educational achievement, the scientific literature also reports the important role of EI in the health sector (Vlachou et al., 2016). Indeed, as this type of profession is centered on technical care and compassion, it requires an important emotional commitment, the latter influencing the quality of care. When nurses understand, identify, and manage their own emotions and the patients' ones, the patient's satisfaction increases (Dugue et al., 2021). As for nursing education, several studies showed the correlation between emotional competences and achievement in nurse school too. Nurse students with higher EI experience a higher resilience (Cleary et al., 2018), better chances of success (Singh et al., 2020), and manage stress and anxiety in a more efficient way than students with lower EI (Lewis et al., 2017).

In the field of social work and health, research shows the positive effects of EI on abilities to think, empathy, psychological health and resilience of social workers (Grant & Kinman, 2012; Grant et al., 2014). Despite the large literature covering the positive link between EI and

success at school, especially in social and health sector, this subject has not been investigated in the VET context.

At the same time, in the Swiss context, training in the health and social care sectors has a very high rate of apprentices: it is in fact one of the ten most chosen occupations in dual initial VET (State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation [SERI], 2022). Consequently, a significant number of young professionals enter the labor market with a consequent amount of job-related competences, but which do not necessarily and explicitly include the emotional ones. In this sense, it is legitimate to ask to what extent these competences - reflecting emotional intelligence - are present in apprenticeships and, above all, what role they play in explaining achievement in vocational education and training.

1.2 Research goals

Based on the current literature reporting the positive influence of EI on academic and professional achievements, the present study aims to investigate the influence of EI on training achievement in VET context and more especially in the health and social care sectors. According to the literature on EI, we consider the two constructs of EI, ability and personality trait, to investigate the influence of both EI's components on training achievement in VET context. We posit the EI as ability and as personality trait will positively influence the grades of apprentices in health and social care sectors.

2 Method

2.1 Participants

An online survey was completed by 110 dual initial VET apprentices in health and social care professions in a French-speaking Swiss vocational school. After exclusion of participants that did not fully complete the survey and after obtaining the grades from the final exam, 92 participants were retained (77 females and 15 males; age: $M=21.64$, $SD=2.63$). All participants gave their consent to participate to this study.

2.2 Procedure and Instruments

To test our hypotheses, we conducted an online survey on the 3rd (and last) year VET apprentices in health and social care sectors. The survey lasted about 25 minutes and was completed on a voluntary basis during school time. All participants gave their consent to participate in the study and allowed us to collect their grades at the end of the training program. The online survey was composed of several sections, each of them measuring the variables of interest, which are detailed below.

The Situational Test of Emotional Understanding (STEU; (MacCann & Roberts, 2008), (translated in French for this study) assessing EI as ability by responding to 25 vignettes that illustrate different situations triggering emotions. Respondents were then asked to choose which of several emotions would be expected in each situation. The Cronbach alpha was .40¹ in our sample. A global score was calculated with the total number of correct answers (score ranging from 0 to 40).

The Ten Items Personality Inventory (TIPI; (Storme et al., 2016), which assesses five personality traits, i.e., extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, emotional stability, and

¹ The STEU shows this low Cronbach alpha pattern because items do not aim to achieve coherence between the responses as self-reports do (Neubauer & Hofer, 2022).

openness on a Likert scale (1=“strongly disagree” to 7=“strongly agree”). The Cronbach alpha was .45² in our sample.

A shortened version of the Raven Standard Progressive Matrices (RAPM; (Raven & Court, 1998), measuring general intelligence by showing 36 matrices of black and white patterns. with a maximal duration of 5 minutes. The Cronbach alpha was .91 in our sample. The score was calculated by summing the correct items (score ranging from 0 to 36).

The Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire (TEIQue; (Mikolajczak et al., 2007), assessing EI as personality trait by answering 30 statements about one’s emotions on a Likert scale (1=“strongly disagree” to 7=“strongly agree”), divided into four sub-dimensions (well-being, self-control, emotionality and sociability) and a global mean. The Cronbach alpha was .85 in our sample.

Participants also answered some sociodemographic questions (sex, age, training profession, etc.). In addition, a prior agreement with the participants and the vocational school had been reached to obtain the final exam grades. These range from 1 to 6, with sufficiency set at 4 and 6 being the best grade.

3 Results

To test our hypotheses, we started by calculating the correlations between the different variables considered in this study. Among the significant correlations (see Table 1), we observed that ability EI (i.e., STEU) correlates significantly and positively with classical intelligence (i.e., Raven) as stated in the literature (Olderbak et al., 2018). Moreover, according to the literature (Chamorro-Premuzic et al., 2007), trait EI (i.e., TEIQue) correlates with all five personality traits measured. Regarding the global grade, it shows significant positive correlations with sex, ability EI and trait EI.

Subsequently, we conducted hierarchical regression analyses (see Table 2) on the influence of EI as trait and ability on grades. Thus, as recommended in the literature (Becker, 2016), the first model included socio-demographic variables (gender, age and school orientation); then, the second model included two measures "classically" considered as predictors of school achievement were added to the regression model: “classical” intelligence (measured here with the short version of Raven matrices (Raven & Court, 1998) and personality (Storme et al., 2016). Finally, the two forms of emotional intelligence were inserted in the third model.

The results of the hierarchical regression showed first of all that gender has a significant relationship on the final score, $\beta=.23$, $t(88)=2.13$, $p=.04$. Moreover, the second model revealed that neither “classical” intelligence nor personality are significant predictors of training achievement, personality. On the contrary, the third model shows that the two forms of emotional intelligence significantly explain the scores obtained in the exams on top of all the other variables (EI as ability $\beta=.31$, $t(85)=2.82$, $p<.01$; EI as personality trait $\beta=.32$, $t(89)=2.08$, $p=.04$).

4 Discussion and conclusions

The present study aimed to investigate the role of EI as ability and personality trait on training achievement in the VET context, using the final exams grades obtained by the participants as an objective measure of achievement. Our results confirm our hypotheses showing that ability and trait EI can be considered as predictors of training achievement in the social and healthcare VET sectors. Indeed, our study demonstrates that apprentices with higher levels of EI succeed better in their apprenticeship.

² The TIPI is composed of only 2 items for each factor, which leads to a low alpha.

Moreover, and contrary to what had been put forward in the literature, it seems that “classical” - i.e., intelligence and personality - do not explain VET achievement. Although non-significant results need to be interpreted with caution, this interesting result seems to reflect the fact that, in occupations where the relationship with others is particularly salient, EI seems to be a stronger predictor of training achievement than cognitive factors. Moreover, we observed a significant correlation between the gender and the final exam grades. We attribute this result to the distribution of the population in the specific health and social care sectors, where women are particularly prevalent. Given the fact that men were only 16% of the sample, we would not consider this effect as relevant in our study.

As further direction, although the present results did not provide any link between EI and sustainability, it would deserve more attention. Indeed, EI should be considered as a relevant variable in research in sustainability positing that high EI would lead to increase the motivation to develop an environment more sustainable.

To conclude, our study provides interesting new findings showing the crucial role of EI as ability and as personality trait on training achievement in the health and social care sectors. This study opens new leads on how emotional competences are involved in school and professional successes and thus would need to be given more attention in training in multiple aspects.

Authors note

We have no conflicts of interest to disclose. This study did not benefit from any funding. Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Laure Tremonte-Freydefont, Avenue de Longemalle, 1, 1020 Renens, Switzerland, laure.tremonte@hefp.swiss

References

- Becker, T. E. (2016). Potential Problems in the Statistical Control of Variables in Organizational Research: A Qualitative Analysis With Recommendations. *Organizational Research Methods*, 8(3), 274-289. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094428105278021>
- Bughin, J., Hazan, E., Lund, S., Dahlström, P., Wiesinger, A., & Subramaniam, A. (2018). Skill shift: Automation and the future of the workforce. *McKinsey Global Institute*, 1, 3-84.
- Chamorro-Premuzic, T., Bennett, E., & Furnham, A. (2007). The happy personality: Medial role of trait emotional intelligence. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 42(8), 1633-1639. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2006.10.029>
- Chinedu, C. C., Saleem, A., & Wan Muda, W. H. N. (2023). Teaching and Learning Approaches: Curriculum Framework for Sustainability Literacy for Technical and Vocational Teacher Training Programmes in Malaysia. *Sustainability*, 15(3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15032543>
- Cleary, M., Visentin, D., West, S., Lopez, V., & Kornhaber, R. (2018). Promoting emotional intelligence and resilience in undergraduate nursing students: An integrative review. *Nurse Educ Today*, 68, 112-120. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2018.05.018>
- Di Fabio, A., & Kenny, M. E. (2015). The Contributions of Emotional Intelligence and Social Support for Adaptive Career Progress Among Italian Youth. *Journal of Career Development*, 42(1), 48-59. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0894845314533420>
- Di Fabio, A., & Saklofske, D. (2019). Positive Relational Management for Sustainable Development: Beyond Personality Traits—The Contribution of Emotional Intelligence. *Sustainability*, 11(2). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11020330>
- Dowling, K., Simpkin, A. J., & Barry, M. M. (2019). A Cluster Randomized-Controlled Trial of the MindOut Social and Emotional Learning Program for Disadvantaged Post-

- Primary School Students. *J Youth Adolesc*, 48(7), 1245-1263. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-019-00987-3>
- Dugue, M., Sirost, O., & Dosseville, F. (2021). A literature review of emotional intelligence and nursing education. *Nurse Educ Pract*, 54, 103124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2021.103124>
- Grant, L., & Kinman, G. (2012). Enhancing Wellbeing in Social Work Students: Building Resilience in the Next Generation. *Social Work Education*, 31(5), 605-621. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02615479.2011.590931>
- Grant, L., Kinman, G., & Alexander, K. (2014). What's All this Talk About Emotion? Developing Emotional Intelligence in Social Work Students. *Social Work Education*, 33(7), 874-889. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02615479.2014.891012>
- Lewis, G. M., Neville, C., & Ashkanasy, N. M. (2017). Emotional intelligence and affective events in nurse education: A narrative review. *Nurse Educ Today*, 53, 34-40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2017.04.001>
- MacCann, C., Jiang, Y., Brown, L. E. R., Double, K. S., Bucich, M., & Minbashian, A. (2020). Emotional intelligence predicts academic performance: A meta-analysis. *Psychol Bull*, 146(2), 150-186. <https://doi.org/10.1037/bul0000219>
- MacCann, C., & Roberts, R. D. (2008). New paradigms for assessing emotional intelligence: theory and data. *Emotion*, 8(4), 540-551. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0012746>
- Mikolajczak, M., Luminet, O., Leroy, C., & Roy, E. (2007). Psychometric properties of the Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire: factor structure, reliability, construct, and incremental validity in a French-speaking population. *J Pers Assess*, 88(3), 338-353. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00223890701333431>
- Nathanson, L., Rivers, S. E., Flynn, L. M., & Brackett, M. A. (2016). Creating Emotionally Intelligent Schools With RULER. *Emotion Review*, 8(4), 305-310. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1754073916650495>
- Neubauer, A. C., & Hofer, G. (2022). (Retest-)Reliable and valid despite low alphas? An example from a typical performance situational judgment test of emotional management. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2022.111511>
- Olderbak, S., Semmler, M., & Doebler, P. (2018). Four-Branch Model of Ability Emotional Intelligence With Fluid and Crystallized Intelligence: A Meta-Analysis of Relations. *Emotion Review*, 11(2), 166-183. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1754073918776776>
- Petrides, K. V., & Furnham, A. (2020). Trait emotional intelligence: psychometric investigation with reference to established trait taxonomies. *European Journal of Personality*, 15(6), 425-448. <https://doi.org/10.1002/per.416>
- Raven, J. C., & Court, J. H. (1998). *Raven's progressive matrices and vocabulary scales*. Oxford Psychologists Press Oxford.
- Sauli, F., Wenger, M., & Fiori, M. (2022). Emotional competences in vocational education and training: state of the art and guidelines for interventions. *Empirical Research in Vocational Education and Training*, 14(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40461-022-00132-8>
- Singh, N., Kulkarni, S., & Gupta, R. (2020). Is emotional intelligence related to objective parameters of academic performance in medical, dental, and nursing students: A systematic review. *Educ Health (Abingdon)*, 33(1), 8-12. https://doi.org/10.4103/efh.EfH_208_17
- Storme, M., Tavani, J.-L., & Myszkowski, N. (2016). Psychometric Properties of the French Ten-Item Personality Inventory (TIPI). *Journal of Individual Differences*, 37(2), 81-87. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1614-0001/a000204>

Vlachou, E. M., Damigos, D., Lyrakos, G., Chanopoulos, K., Kosmidis, G., & Miltiades, K. (2016). the Relationship between Burnout Syndrome and Emotional Intelligence in Healthcare Professionals. *Health Science Journal*, 10(5.2). <https://doi.org/10.4172/1791-809X.1000100502>

Biographical notes

Dr **Laure Tremonte-Freydefont** is a senior researcher at the Swiss Federal University for Vocational Education and Training. Her interests in the field of emotional intelligence and motivation are highly innovative in the VET context.

Prof. Dr. **Marina Fiori** is head of research field *Teaching and learning processes* at the Swiss Federal University for Vocational Education and Training. Her main domain of expertise are emotional intelligence, emotional competences and hypersensibility. She conducts research on the topic of emotion, learning, and socio-emotional competences in vocational education and training.

Dr **Matilde Wenger** is a scientific collaborator at the Swiss Federal University for Vocational Education and Training. Her topics of interest are in-company trainers' conditions and needs for continuing education; dual VET quality; dual apprentices' role stress. Her research areas are based on social psychology, educational sciences and sociology. She favours mixed methodological approaches and works with both quantitative and qualitative approaches.